

Galeommatoida (Bivalvia) from Namibia (Part 2)

Galeommatoida (Bivalvia) de Namibia (Parte 2)

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ABSTRACT

This work presents the second part of a study of the superfamily Galeommatoida (Bivalvia) found on the continental shelf and upper bathyal slope off Namibia, SW Africa. One new species is proposed: *Saxicavella trapezia* n. sp. Three species (*Galeomma turtoni* W. Turton, 1825, *Planktomya magna* Gofas, 2000 and *Kellia suborbicularis* (Montagu, 1803)) are reported for the first time from Namibia. A fourth species (of the genus *Lasaea*), which is known from the literature, has not yet been confirmed.

RESUMEN

En este trabajo se presenta la segunda parte de un estudio de la superfamilia Galeommatoida (Bivalvia) de la plataforma continental y del talud batial superior frente a Namibia, en el suroeste de África. Se propone una nueva especie: *Saxicavella trapezia* n. sp. Tres especies (*Galeomma turtoni* W. Turton, 1825, *Planktomya magna* Gofas, 2000 y *Kellia suborbicularis* (Montagu, 1803)) se citan por primera vez de Namibia. Una cuarta especie (del género *Lasaea*), conocida en la literatura, aún no ha sido confirmada.

KEY WORDS: Mollusca, Basterotiidae, Lasaeidae, *Galeomma*, *Lasaea*, *Kellia*, *Planktomya*, *Saxicavella*, SE Atlantic Ocean, SW Africa.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, Basterotiidae, Lasaeidae, *Galeomma*, *Lasaea*, *Kellia*, *Planktomya*, *Saxicavella*, SE Océano Atlántico, SW África.

INTRODUCTION

Galeommatoida Gray, 1840 is one of the most species-rich bivalve superfamilies (HUBER, 2015). GOTO, ISHIKAWA & HAMAMURA (2012) provided a molecular analysis and proved that the superfamily is polyphyletic below the supra-familial classification. Only species in Basterotiidae Cossmann, 1909 formed a single clade and hence supported a family. We herein

follow GOTO ET AL. (2012) and consider the separation between Galeommatidae and Lasaeidae as taxonomically uncertain.

A historic overview of regional references to Galeommatoida was given in ZETTLER & HOFFMAN (2021). They also reported on six species in the genera *Kurtiella* Gofas & Salas, 2008, *Bornia* Philippi, 1836 and *Scacchia* Philippi, 1844

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and they introduced four new species. Based on newly obtained materials from the expedition with the R/V Maria S. Merian (MSM105) and the evaluation of cores from the cruise with R/V Meteor (M122), further species and genera of this superfamily were found, which will be discussed herein. In the present study, we report on additional poorly-known and new galeommatoid species from Namibia in four genera: *Galeomma* W. Turton, 1825, *Kellia* W. Turton, 1822, *Planktomya* Simroth, 1896 and *Saxicavella* P. Fischer, 1878. Some nomenclatural notes are given for a *Lasaea* species reported by PENRITH & KENSLEY (1970a, b) in shallow Namibian waters. We have seen no Namibian material for the latter species yet.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material for this study was collected during two cruises of the research vessels Maria S. Merian (MSM105) and Meteor (M122) off the coast of Namibia (HEBBELN *ET AL.*, 2017). Sediment samples

were obtained using van Veen grabs, box-corers, gravity-corers and dredges. The sediment samples were sieved by washing retaining the fractions larger than 1 mm. Live-collected specimens were fixed in formalin, sorted, and identified in the laboratory. The shells in the samples from cruise M122 were obtained from thanatocoenoses in seafloor sediments. Sieve fractions >1 mm were sorted for molluscs using a stereo-microscope with low magnification (6–60×). Some shells and specimens were colour-photographed using a light microscope at IOW while others were prepared for scanning electron microscope (SEM) imaging at IOW and SaM.

The type material has been deposited at the Senckenberg Museum Frankfurt (SMF), while other reference materials are kept at the IOW.

Abbreviations

SaM – Senckenberg am Meer, Wilhelmshaven (Germany);
SMF – Senckenberg Museum Frankfurt (Germany);
IOW – Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research, Warnemünde (Germany).

SYSTEMATIC RESULTS

Class BIVALVIA Linnaeus, 1758
Superfamily GALEOMMATOIDEA Gray, 1840
Family GALEOMMATIDAE Gray, 1840
Genus *Galeomma* W. Turton, 1825

Type species: *Galeomma turtoni* W. Turton, 1825 (type by monotypy).

Galeomma turtoni W. Turton, 1825 (Fig. 1)

Galeomma turtoni W. TURTON, 1825: 361-362, pl. 1, fig. 1; GOFAS, 1991: 344-346, figs. 1-5; GÓMEZ & PÉREZ, 1998: 226; GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011: 614; HERNÁNDEZ *ET AL.* 2011: 340, fig. 113M; HUBER, 2015: 108-109, 467; COSEL & GOFAS, 2019: 472, fig. 11.1.

Material investigated: NAMIBIA • 1 live-collected specimen (Fig. 1A-E); 18.000°S, 11.7916°E; 20 m; 23 Jan. 2022; MSM105 sta. 46; dredge.

Remarks: We found this species on hard substrates at Rocky Point in northern Namibia at a water depth of 20 metres. Previously, it was only known from the southern British Isles, the

Mediterranean Sea to Senegal and the Canary Islands and a single record in northern Angola (GOFAS 1991; COSEL & GOFAS 2019). The present record extends the known distribution to Namibia.

Figure 1. *Galeomma turtoni* W. Turton, 1825, Namibia, MSM105 sta. 46, live-collected, length 4.4 mm. A: dorsal view; B: enlarged view of the umbonal area, prodisoconch length 0.20 mm; C: ventral view; D, E: external lateral view.

Figura 1. *Galeomma turtoni* W. Turton, 1825, Namibia, MSM105 sta. 46, recolectados vivos, longitud 4,4 mm. A: vista dorsal; B: vista aumentada de la región umbonal, longitud de la prodisoconcha 0,20 mm; C: vista ventral; D, E: vista lateral externa.

Family BASTEROTIIDAE Cossmann, 1909

Genus *Saxicavella* P. Fischer, 1878

Type species: *Mytilus plicatus* Gmelin, 1791 *sensu* Montagu, 1808 accepted as *Saxicavella jeffreysi* Winckworth, 1930 (type by monotypy).

Saxicavella trapezia n. sp. (Fig. 2)

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Type material. *Holotype*: NAMIBIA • 1 live-collected specimen (Fig. 2G-H); MSM105 sta. 88; 27.000°S, 14.083°E; 419 m; 03 Feb. 2022; dredge; SMF373057. *Paratypes*: NAMIBIA • 15 live-collected specimens; same location as for holotype; SMF373058 • 7 live-collected specimens; MSM105 sta. 89; 27.000°S, 14.267°E; 383 m; 03 Feb. 2022; dredge; SMF373059 • 1 live-collected specimen; MSM105 sta. 90; 27.000°S, 14.450°E; 339 m; 04 Feb. 2022; van Veen grab; SMF373060.

Type locality: Namibia, SW off Lüderitz, 27.000°S, 14.083°E, 419 m.

Etymology: The name indicates the trapezoidal outline.

Diagnosis: Small flattened, translucent, fragile shell, equivalve, inequilateral, with flattened dorsal margin, convex anterior, posterior obliquely truncated, ventral outline widely convex; umbos blunt, elevated inclined anteriorly. Valves gaping anteriorly and postero-dorsally, both valves with large posterior rounded tooth; colour translucent white, animal yellowish to pink. Dimensions length 6.4 mm, height 4.1 mm, tumidity of two valves 2.3 mm (Figs 2A–H).

Description: Prodissoconch single stage. Subcircular; nucleus well rounded, protruding, with rough sculpture; marginal area smooth (Fig. 2D); dimensions height 0.24 mm, length 0.28 mm.

Dissoconch outline with long straightened dorsal margin, weakly convex anteriorly and posteriorly, transition to posterior margin pointed at about 120°, posterior margin weakly convex and pointed at transition to ventral margin at about 80°. Umbo small, weakly pronounced (Figs 2A–E, G). External sculpture with numerous irregular, coarse growth stages. Brown short external ligament behind umbos. Periostracum light straw. Shell internally smooth and imprint of external undulations; sharp smooth shell margin; one ridge from umbo to inside of anterior muscle scar, a second weaker ridge from umbo to the central posterior area; pallial line and muscle scars inconspicuous, no sinus. Straight hinge plates below umbo; lateral teeth lacking (Figs 2C, E). Left valve with one posterior pronounced tooth close to margin and one small knob anterior of umbo; right valve with symmetrical marginal tooth posteriorly, rounded; deep nymph at margin.

Variability: Little variability observed; length up to 6.4 mm.

Differential diagnosis: Placement in the genus *Saxicavella* is based on the

similarity with the type species *S. jeffreysi*; generic characteristics include the thin obliquely drawn shells with irregular growth lines and the hinge with a single elongated posterior tooth in both valves.

The present species can be differentiated by the trapezoidal outline and the truncated posterior margin. We found no sympatric congeners in Namibia. The north-eastern Atlantic type species *S. jeffreysi* has a triangular outline with a straightened ventral margin and a protruding umbo; SCOTT (1994: fig. 6) appointed and figured the lectotype. The eastern Pacific *S. pacifica* Dall, 1916 is very similar to the type species with a very convex anterior margin (SCOTT 1994: holotype in fig. 7). *Saxicavella sagrinata* Dall & Simpson (1901) was described from off Puerto Rico; the species has a wide triangular outline with convex margins (SCOTT 1994: holotype in fig. 8); the outline of the present species is less triangular and the anterior margin is less convex. The Californian *S. nybakkeni* Scott, 1994 has a compact rhomboidal outline rather than a trapezoidal outline with posterior truncation in the present species.

Remarks: The present species is solely known from the type material off Lüderitz, 27.000°S, 339–419 m. The species was found alive on the lower shelf and is very probably associated with a spoon worm (Echiurida) like others observed by GOTO ET AL. (2016). Stations which yielded large spoon worms were always characterised by this species.

SCOTT (1994) discussed the reproductive biology of *S. nybakkeni*; the species proved to be simultaneous hermaphrodite. Moreover, his species provided brood protection for embryos between mantle folds. It is likely that the present species has similar traits.

Family LASAEIDAE J. E. Gray, 1842 (uncertain classification)

Genus *Kellia* W. Turton, 1822

Type species: *Kellia suborbicularis* (Montagu, 1803) (type by subsequent designation).

Figure 2. *Saxicavella trapezia* n. sp., Namibia, MSM105 sta. 88. A-F. Paratypes, SMF373058. A: left valve, external view, height 3.6 mm, length 5.8 mm; B: right valve, external view, height 3.5 mm, length 5.5 mm; C, D: left valve, internal view, height 2.8 mm, length 4.6 mm; E, F: right valve, internal view, height 2.8 mm, length 4.6 mm. G, H. Holotype, SMF373057, external view right valve (G), dorsal view (H), height 4.1 mm, length 6.4 mm, tumidity (two valves) 2.3 mm.

Figura 2. *Saxicavella trapezia* n. sp., Namibia, MSM105 sta. 88. A-F. Paratipos, SMF SMF373058. A: valva izquierda, vista externa, altura 3,6 mm, longitud 5,8 mm; B: valva derecha, vista externa, altura 3,5 mm, longitud 5,5 mm; C, D: valva izquierda, vista interna, altura 2,8 mm, longitud 4,6 mm; E, F: valva derecha, vista interna, altura 2,8 mm, longitud 4,6 mm. G, H. Holotipo, SMF373057, vista externa de la valva derecha (G), vista dorsal (H), altura 4,1 mm, longitud 6,4 mm, tumidez (dos valvas) 2,3 mm.

Figure 3. *Kellia suborbicularis* (Montagu, 1803), Namibia, M122 sta. GeoB 20516. A-C. Left valve. A: inside view, length 4.2 mm; B: umbonal view; C: hinge and prodissoconch, length 0.4 mm. D-F. Right valve. D: internal view, length 4.0 mm; E: umbonal view; F: hinge and prodissoconch; G: right valve, external view, length 4.0 mm.

Figura 3. *Kellia suborbicularis* (Montagu, 1803), Namibia, M122 sta. GeoB 20516. A-C. Valva izquierda. A: vista interior, longitud 4,2 mm; B: vista umbonal; C: charnela y prodisococha, longitud 0,4 mm. D-F. Valva derecha. D: vista interna, longitud 4,0 mm; E: vista umbonal; F: charnela y prodisococha; G: valva derecha, vista externa, longitud 4,0 mm.

Kellia suborbicularis (Montagu, 1803) (Fig. 3)

Mya suborbicularis MONTAGU, 1803: 39.

Kellia suborbicularis: LEBOUR, 1938: 447–451; TEBBLE, 1966: 83–84 figs 37a–c; COSEL & GOFAS, 2019: 486, fig. 11.15; see ZETTLER & ALF, 2021: 124–125, plate 47, for a comprehensive chresonymy.

Material investigated: NAMIBIA • 5 valves; 20.764°S, 12.831°E; 219 m; 03 Jan. 2016; M122 sta. GeoB 20516; box core • 1 valve; 20°43.467'S, 12°50.736'E; 165 m; 04 Jan. 2016; M122 sta. GeoB 20529; gravity core; core depth 55–60 cm • 2 valves; 20.907 °S, 12.892°E; 224 m; 07 Jan. 2016; M122 sta. GeoB 20561; van Veen grab • 3 live-collected specimens; 18.000°S, 11.792°E; 20 m; 23 Jan. 2022; MSM105 sta. 43; dredge.

Remarks: This Atlantic species is known from NW Europe, the Mediterranean Sea, Azores, NW Africa to Cape Verde Islands and Senegal, Angola (COSEL & GOFAS 2019: 486). The species has also been reported from Port Elizabeth, South Africa (SOWERBY 1892, p. 62), but there are contradictory taxonomic classifications to *Kellia becki* (W. H. Turton, 1932) and *Kellia rotunda* (Des-

hayes, 1856). HUBER (2015, p. 498) notes that without genetic data a synonymy is speculative. Genetic verification is definitely required here. The present study fills the knowledge gap for SW Africa (Namibia, 18° – 20.9°S, 20 – 224 m).

The species is characterised by a sub-circular outline and the hinge with one posterior lateral tooth and two anterior teeth in each valve.

Figure 4. *Planktomya magna* Gofas, 2000, Namibia, M122 sta. GeoB 20515. A: external view of left valve, length 6 mm; B: prodissoconch, length 1.5 mm; C: umbonal view of left valve; D: internal view, length 7 mm; E: hinge; F: external view of right valve, length 8 mm; G: prodissoconch; H: umbonal view of right valve; I: internal view, length 8 mm; J: hinge.

Figura 4. *Planktomya magna* Gofas, 2000, Namibia, M122 sta. GeoB 20515. A: vista externa de la valva izquierda, longitud 6 mm; B: prodissoconcha, longitud 1,5 mm; C: vista umbonal de la valva izquierda; D: vista interna, longitud 7 mm; E: charnela; F: vista externa de la valva derecha, longitud 8 mm; G: prodissoconcha; H: vista umbonal de la valva derecha; I: vista interna, longitud 8 mm; J: charnela.

LEBOUR (1938) and SCHIAPARELLI, COVAZZI & ALBERTELLI (2021) extensively reported on the viviparous development of incubating larvae, followed by a planktonic stage where veligers may reach a

length of 0.3–0.4 mm at metamorphosis. Adults may reach a length of up to 9 mm. Adult specimens live in rubble of rocks and shells or in crevices, holes and holdfasts of seaweeds (POPHAM, 1940).

Genus *Planktomya* Simroth, 1896

Type species: *Planktomya henseni* Simroth, 1896 (type by monotypy), Caribbean Sea.

Planktomya magna Gofas, 2000 (Fig. 4)

Planktomya magna GOFAS, 2000: 1014, 1019–1020, fig. 5a–e; COSEL & GOFAS, 2019: 504, fig. 11.34.

Material investigated: NAMIBIA • 3 valves; 20.764°S, 12.833°E; 226 m; 03 Jan. 2016; box core • 5 valves; 20.718°S, 12.837°E; 182 m; 03 Jan. 2016; M122 sta. GeoB 20523; M122 sta. GeoB 20515; gravity core • 1 valve; 20.717°S, 12.867°E; 178 m; 04 Jan. 2016; M122 sta. GeoB 20532; van Veen grab.

Remarks: The species is known from single valves only from Cape Verde and Angola, water depth 10 – 20 m (GOFAS 2000; COSEL & GOFAS 2019) and in Namibia, 20.7° – 20.8°S, 178 – 226 m (this study).

Planktomya species are rare as adults (GOFAS 2000). In contrast, the larvae are

common in many plankton samples from the Atlantic. Species in this genus are characterized by long-lasting planktonic life phases. The shell is characterised by the large prodissoconch and the fissure in the nucleus of the prodissoconch.

DISCUSSION

In the older literature, several dozen species of the Galeommatoidae (e.g. SOWERBY 1892; SMITH 1904; BARTSCH 1915; TURTON 1932) are reported from South Africa (only very few records belong to Namibia), many of which were later withdrawn due to revisions. BARNARD (1964) still lists about 19 taxa of this superfamily. In KILBURN & RIPPEY (1982) only five species were listed, but most of the species were probably ignored due to their small size. Finally, HUBER (2015) listed around 32 species of this superfamily for South Africa, 14 for Angola but only three for Namibia. ZETTLER & HOFFMAN (2021) reported six species off Namibia of which four were new to science. For two species (*Kurtiella bidentata* and *K. ovata*) the knowledge of the distribution could be extended considerably. The present study adds four more species with one species new to science. For three species (*Galeomma turtoni*, *Kellia suborbicularis* and *Plankto-*

mya magna) the knowledge of their distribution could also be considerably improved.

PENRITH & KENSLEY (1970a, b) reported for several nearshore places along the Namibian coast observations of *Kellya rubra* (Montagu, 1803) [now *Lasaea rubra* (Montagu, 1803)]. There are currently three *Lasaea* species known or described from southern Africa: *Lasaea rubra* (Montagu, 1803), *Lasaea turtoni* Bartsch, 1915 and *Lasaea adansoni* (Gmelin, 1791). In the present study, we were unable to make any records of *Lasaea* in Namibia ourselves. Due to the lack of material, a taxonomic classification is therefore not possible and we refrain from going into more detail.

Saxicavella (Basterotiidae) from the eastern Pacific and the Atlantic comprises only five described species (SCOTT 1994; HUBER 2015; this study). Shells of the type species *S. jeffreysi* have been found off NW Africa (Morocco and Mau-

ritania, unpublished data). Currently, *S. trapezia* n. sp. is the only congener occurring off south-western Africa. The species in the genus are probably commensals with spoon worms (Echiurida).

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